

Assessing the Efficacy of Fentanyl vs. Magnesium Sulfate as Adjuvants to 0.375% Bupivacaine in Ultrasound-Guided Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aim: Magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄) has emerged as a promising adjuvant in brachial plexus block, yielding positive outcomes. Nevertheless, the medical community has yet to reach a consensus on the ideal dosing parameters. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of adding magnesium sulphate (150 mg) and fentanyl (50 microgrammes) to 0.375% bupivacaine compared to a placebo in the context of supraclavicular brachial plexus block.

Material and Methods: A prospective study was carried out following the approval of the institutional ethical committee at a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India, spanning a duration of one year. A total of 150 patients, regardless of gender, classified as American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) grade I or II, were included in the study. These patients were scheduled for upper limb surgeries located distal to the mid-humerus, which were performed using an ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block. In this study, participants were randomly assigned to one of three groups, each consisting of 50 individuals. Group A received 20ml of 0.375% Bupivacaine, Group B was administered 150 mg of Magnesium sulphate alongside Bupivacaine, and Group C received 50 microgrammes of Fentanyl in combination with Bupivacaine. The main objective of the study was to evaluate the onset and quality of both sensory and motor blockade across all three groups.

Results: A statistically significant difference in VAS scores was observed among the three groups from 6 to 18 hours following the block procedure. The VAS scores did not show significant differences at the 6 and 24-hour time points, with the mean post-operative VAS score being lower in Group C compared to Groups B and A. The onset time of sensory blockade showed no significant difference between groups C and B ($p > 0.05$). However, group A exhibited a markedly shorter onset time when compared to both groups C and B individually ($p < 0.001$). The average time for motor blockade to begin was similar in groups C and B (p value > 0.05), while group A experienced a significantly quicker onset of motor block.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that fentanyl, when used as an adjuvant, offers enhanced analgesic effects compared to both magnesium sulphate and placebo, particularly in terms of the duration of motor and sensory blockade.

Keywords: Bupivacaine, Fentanyl, Magnesium Sulphate, Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block.

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Introduction

The supraclavicular brachial plexus block stands out as a reliable and cost-effective method, offering optimal conditions for surgical procedures along with significant post-operative pain relief. The use of ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block enhances the visualisation of underlying structures, facilitates needle movement, and ensures direct spread of local anaesthetic. This approach significantly improves the safety and effectiveness of the procedure when compared to

the traditional nerve stimulator-guided technique. [1] Despite the availability of several newer medications, bupivacaine remains a commonly utilised local anaesthetic for supraclavicular blocks. Its long duration of action, lasting over 3 to 6 hours, coupled with effective motor blockade, contributes to its continued preference in clinical practice. While the duration of action of local anaesthetics in brachial plexus blocks can offer effective intraoperative anaesthesia, the

diminishing effects of the dense block pose a significant challenge during the postoperative period. [2] The addition of two specific additives to local anaesthetics used in brachial plexus blocks has been shown to improve both the quality and duration of analgesia. [3] Vasoconstrictors have been employed to extend sensory blockade; however, the outcomes have been either inconclusive or linked to adverse effects. [4-6] The anti-nociceptive action of Magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄), attributed to its regulation of calcium influx into cells and antagonism of N-methyl D-aspartate receptors, has been utilised to enhance both the quality and duration of analgesia in supraclavicular brachial plexus block. [7] Multiple studies have indicated that the administration of per-neural MgSO₄ during general anaesthesia can lead to a decrease in the required dosage of anaesthetics and a reduction in the need for postoperative pain relief. [8-10] Nevertheless, an examination of the existing literature regarding the application of MgSO₄ as an adjunct to supraclavicular brachial plexus block uncovers studies that present inconsistent findings. The precise dosage of MgSO₄ for brachial plexus block remains undetermined.

The antinociceptive properties of fentanyl begin with the activation of peripheral opioid receptors. [11] This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of adding magnesium sulphate (150 mg) and fentanyl (50 microgrammes) to 0.375% bupivacaine, compared to a placebo, in the context of supraclavicular brachial plexus block.

Material and Methods

A prospective study was carried out following the approval of the institutional ethical committee at a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India, spanning a duration of one year. A total of 150 patients, regardless of gender, classified as American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) grade I or II, were included in the study. These individuals were scheduled for upper limb surgeries located distal to the mid-humerus, which were performed using an ultrasound-guided supraclavicular brachial plexus block. Individuals classified as ASA grade 3 or higher, those with known hypersensitivity to the study medications, lactating or pregnant individuals, and patients with hepatic, cardiac, or renal abnormalities were excluded from the study. Additionally, participants on long-term analgesic therapy, those with comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, bleeding disorders, local skin infections, contraindications to supraclavicular brachial plexus block, and individuals who declined to participate were also not included.

The calculation of sample size was conducted with reference to a prior study conducted by Yaghoobi et al [6]. A total of 150 patients, with 50

participants in each group, were included in the study to achieve a minimum power of 90%. This design also aimed to minimise the alpha error to 5% and account for a 10% attrition rate. Patients were assigned to three groups through a block randomisation method, utilising a computer-generated random number table as follows:

In this study, three distinct groups were analysed for their respective treatments. Group A consisted of 50 participants receiving 20ml of 0.375% Bupivacaine combined with 2 ml of Normal Saline. Group B, also with 50 participants, was administered 20ml of 0.375% Bupivacaine along with 150 mg of magnesium sulphate. Lastly, Group C included 50 participants who received 20ml of 0.375% Bupivacaine paired with 50 microgrammes of fentanyl.

A comprehensive preanesthetic evaluation and necessary laboratory tests were conducted the day before the surgery. Upon transferring the patient to the operating theatre, all standard ASA monitors were promptly connected. A peripheral intravenous cannula of 18G was placed, and the administration of Ringer's lactate intravenous fluid commenced. The procedure was thoroughly explained to each patient, and the Supraclavicular brachial plexus block was carried out with the assistance of ultrasound guidance. While the patient was in a supine position with the head turned to the opposite side, observations were made regarding the brachial plexus and its relationship to the surrounding anatomical structures. The probe was positioned transversely in the supraclavicular fossa to examine the subclavian artery and the brachial plexus. The subclavian artery appeared as a pulsating hypoechoic structure positioned above the hyperechoic first rib, while the brachial plexus was identified laterally as a cluster of hypoechoic nodules. Following comprehensive aseptic precautions, meticulous skin preparation, and the administration of local anaesthetic infiltration, a 50-mm 22-gauge insulated needle was subsequently introduced laterally to the ultrasound probe utilising the in-plane technique. After the needle accessed the brachial plexus cluster, a tailored local anaesthetic mixture was administered incrementally, following a negative aspiration for blood or air, positioned adjacent to the artery. The needle was subsequently adjusted to deliver the injection at the artery's lower pole. Real-time ultrasound imaging revealed the dispersion of local anaesthetic at the moment of injection. The main aim of the study was to evaluate the onset and quality of sensory blockade across the three groups. Furthermore, the secondary objectives focused on evaluating the differences in motor blockade, postoperative pain management, haemodynamic indicators, and the occurrence of any adverse events among the groups.

The assessment of sensory block was conducted using a pinprick test, evaluated on a three-point scale every two minutes, until either satisfactory sensory blockade for surgery was achieved or a maximum of 30 minutes had elapsed. The evaluation of motor blockade was conducted utilising the modified Bromage scale. Documentation occurred every 2 minutes until satisfactory motor blockade was achieved for surgery or until 30 minutes had elapsed following the block. Following the surgery, measurements were taken every 30 minutes for the first 4 hours, then every 2 hours until the 12-hour mark, and subsequently every 6 hours until 24 hours post-operation.

The onset of sensory blockade was characterised as the interval from the conclusion of the group-specific study drug injection to the point at which sensation to pinprick was lost. The onset of motor blockade was recorded as the duration between the conclusion of the injection and the achievement of complete motor paralysis in the wrist and hand. The duration of sensory blockade refers to the time span from the onset of a sensory blockade score of 1, measured prior to surgery, to the offset of the sensory blockade, indicated by a score of 1 after the procedure, as evaluated through the pin-prick test.

The duration of motor blockade was established as the time span from the onset of a modified Bromage score of 3 to the achievement of a modified Bromage score of 0 following the surgical procedure. The evaluation of pain was conducted utilising a visual analogue scale (VAS), with 0 indicating no pain and 10 representing the most severe pain imaginable. The postoperative VAS score was evaluated every 30 minutes for the first four hours and subsequently whenever the patient reported pain, continuing for a total of 24 hours. Reported experiencing pain for up to 24 hours.

During and after the block procedure, any adverse events such as nausea, vomiting, pruritus, urinary retention, bradycardia, and respiratory depression were documented. Postoperative complications associated with supraclavicular brachial plexus block, such as pneumothorax and phrenic nerve injury, were observed. Patients who experienced patchy sensory blockade and required additional analgesia during or prior to surgery, as well as those who received general anaesthesia, were excluded from further statistical analysis.

Administration via syringe Intravenous administration of 1 mg atropine was utilised for symptomatic bradycardia, while 6 mg of injection mepentermine was given intravenously to address hypotension, specifically in relation to mean arterial pressure (MAP).

The pulse rate (PR), mean arterial pressure (MAP), peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and

respiratory rate (RR) were meticulously documented before and after the block procedure. Measurements were taken at intervals of 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, 60, 120, 180, and 240 minutes, continuing every 6 hours for a full 24 hours post-surgery. The onset time and the percentage of patients requiring rescue analgesia were documented in the study protocol.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was organised and input into a spreadsheet application (Microsoft Excel 2019) before being exported to the data editor interface of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were characterised using means and standard deviations or medians and interquartile ranges, depending on their distribution patterns. Qualitative variables were reported in terms of counts and percentages. The confidence level for all tests was established at 95%, while the level of significance was set at 5%.

Results

The demographic variables, including age, gender, weight, and ASA grade, showed comparability across all three groups (Table 1). The mean values for PR, MAP, SpO₂, and RR showed no significant differences among the three groups, both during and after the surgical procedures, with p-values exceeding 0.05.

The average VAS scores of patients are presented in Table 2. A statistically significant difference in VAS scores was observed among the three groups from 6 to 18 hours following the block procedure. The VAS scores showed no significant differences at the 6 and 24-hour time points, with the mean post-operative VAS score being lower in Group C compared to Groups B and A.

The onset and duration of both sensory and motor blockade are presented in Table 3. The onset time of sensory blockade showed no significant difference between groups C and B ($p > 0.05$). However, group A exhibited a significantly shorter onset time when compared to both group C and group B individually ($p < 0.001$). The average onset time for motor blockade showed no significant difference between groups C and B ($p \text{ value} > 0.05$), while group A exhibited a notably faster onset of motor block. The average duration of sensory blockade was recorded at 7.70 ± 1.50 hours, while motor blockade lasted 8.10 ± 2.50 hours, with group C exhibiting the longest durations in comparison to groups B and A.

The proportion of patients needing rescue analgesia was notably lower in group C compared to both group B and group A. The average duration before the administration of rescue analgesia in groups F, M, and P was recorded as 14.50 ± 5.20 , 10.01 ± 2.49 , and 8.77 ± 3.20 hours, respectively. In the post-1hoc

analysis, the mean time to rescue analgesia showed a significant difference solely between groups C and A ($p < 0.005$). However, no significant

differences were observed between groups C and B ($p > 0.05$) or between groups A and B ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Demographic data of study participants in all groups

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P value
Age (years)	34.98 ± 10.54	35.97 ± 12.47	32.25 ± 10.47	0.45
Weight (kg)	64.90 ± 9.15	62.74 ± 8.56	63.50 ± 8.12	0.12
Gender [n (%)]				
Male	31 (62)	31 (62)	32 (64)	0.09
Female	19 (38)	19 (38)	18 (36)	
ASA Grade				
I	48 (96)	45 (90)	47 (94)	0.35
II	2 (4)	5 (10)	3 (6)	

Statistically significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2: VAS scores in study participants between three groups

Post-operative VAS score	Group A	Group B	Group C	P value
4 hours	0.02 ± 0.01	0	0	0.12
6 hours	0.09 ± 0.3	0.22 ± 0.68	2.09 ± 1.32	0.05*
8 hours	0.30 ± 0.70	1.94 ± 1.28	3.70 ± 1.56	0.03*
12 hours	2.60 ± 1.40	3.50 ± 1.22	3.72 ± 1.11	0.02*
18 hours	3.20 ± 0.57	3.64 ± 0.71	3.87 ± 0.45	0.001
24 hours	3.95 ± 1.15	3.59 ± 0.22	3.87 ± 0.70	0.25

* Indicate statistically significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 3: Duration and onset of sensory as well as motor blockade in study participants

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P value
Onset of sensory block (Minutes)	8.10 ± 2.50	8.54 ± 2.10	4.12 ± 0.99	0.05*
Duration of sensory Blockade (Hours)	7.70 ± 1.50	6.30 ± 0.95	4.20 ± 0.50	0.003*
Onset of motor block (Minutes)	11.20 ± 2.78	11.80 ± 2.44	5.95 ± 0.90	0.002*
Duration of motor block (Hours)	8.20 ± 2.05	6.30 ± 0.90	4.30 ± 0.85	0.02*

Discussion

Among the various trace elements, magnesium stands out as particularly significant. It acts as a competitive antagonist at the N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor and inhibits voltage-dependent ion channels. Furthermore, magnesium has been shown to enhance the duration of the block in regional anaesthesia. Seven Supraclavicular blocks are delivered at the site of the brachial plexus nerve trunk. The three-nerve trunk, located in a compact and easily accessible area, serves as the exclusive sensory, motor, and sympathetic supply for the upper limb. This block leads to a rapid and predictable onset of significant anaesthesia, characterized by a high degree of reliability. Ultrasound offers healthcare professionals immediate visual insights that enhance the identification of anatomical structures, ensure safe needle placement, and facilitate the effective distribution of local anaesthetics. [8] The demographic characteristics of patients showed no statistically significant differences among the three groups and aligned with findings from other research studies, thereby ensuring consistency for comparison purposes. [9,10] The central premise of our investigation focusses on the dose-dependent influence of MgSO₄ as an adjuvant on peripheral

nerves, grounded in the surface charge theory articulated by Akutagawa et al. [11] The researchers proposed that adjusting the external magnesium concentration led to a synergistic effect on nerve blockade when using local anaesthetics. Mert et al. [12] noted that elevated levels of divalent ions, drawn in by the negative charge of the outer membrane surface, influenced Na⁺ channel gating. This interaction could lead to hyperpolarisation, ultimately resulting in a nerve conduction block. The studies referenced indicate that a higher concentration of magnesium (250 mg) resulted in a more significant prolongation of the block. The onset of sensory and motor block was similar between group C and group B; however, the addition of fentanyl and magnesium sulphate resulted in a statistically significant delay in the onset of both sensory and motor block compared to local anaesthetic alone. These findings align with previous research in the field. Contrary to our study findings, Verma et al. observed a faster onset of sensorimotor blockade with magnesium sulphate. [13]

Our findings indicate that the duration of sensory and motor blockade was notably extended in group C in comparison to both group B and group A. In a comparable observation, the length of both sensory

and motor blockade was notably extended in group B when contrasted with group A. Various other researchers have reported similar findings in their studies. [9,14,15] In conclusion, the findings indicate that Fentanyl demonstrates a superior duration of both motor and sensory blockade. In a study conducted by Ozalevli et al., [16] the researchers examined the impact of incorporating intrathecal magnesium sulphate into bupivacaine-fentanyl spinal anaesthesia, comparing it with magnesium combined with 0.9% sodium chloride in patients undergoing lower limb surgery. Their findings indicated that magnesium resulted in a delayed onset of both sensory and motor blocks, while also extending the duration of spinal anaesthesia. A study by Elsharnouby et al. in Cairo in 2008 found that patients receiving intra-articular injections of bupivacaine combined with magnesium experienced longer durations of analgesia compared to those in the control group who received a placebo. [17] A study conducted by Varma et al. revealed that the durations of sensory and motor blocks were significantly extended in Group BM1 compared to BM0.5 and B ($P \leq 0.05$). This finding is particularly noteworthy as magnesium sulphate was utilised as an adjuvant in the earlier group. [13]

In our study, we evaluated postoperative pain through the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) at multiple intervals. The comparison of the VAS score among the three groups revealed a statistically significant difference starting from the sixth hour following the initiation of the block. In a comparison between group C and group B regarding VAS scores, a significant difference was observed starting from the 8th hour, which later became nonsignificant by the 24th hour. There was a notable difference in the requirement for rescue analgesia between groups C and A ($p < 0.05$), while no significant difference was observed between groups C and B ($p > 0.05$).

Furthermore, our observations indicated that the requirement for rescue analgesics was reduced in group B compared to group A; however, this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Comparable findings were reported by Das A et al., Lee AR et al., and EL Shamaa HA et al. in their individual research efforts. Throughout the study, there were no observed complications associated with the block and local anaesthetics in any of the patients involved. The study faced limitations due to its sample size, which could have been expanded to enhance its statistical power. Additionally, incorporating more centres could have facilitated a multicentric approach, potentially yielding more comprehensive results.

Conclusion

Fentanyl, when used as an adjuvant, demonstrated enhanced analgesic effects compared to both Magnesium sulphate and placebo, particularly in terms of prolonging motor and sensory blockade duration. Furthermore, patients administered fentanyl as an adjunct experienced a reduced need for rescue analgesia, and the time to the first instance of rescue analgesia was notably extended for these individuals. Fentanyl demonstrates superior efficacy as an adjuvant compared to magnesium sulphate when combined with bupivacaine for perioperative anaesthesia in upper limb surgeries utilising supraclavicular blocks.

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